

CONCEPT OF METHODS OF GETTING TO KNOW NATURE

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Abstract: This article discusses methods of introducing children to nature in the formation of their knowledge and skills in the educational process.

Key words: Educational process, methodology, natural science, natural sciences, students.

In pedagogy, the method is a collaborative effort aimed at achieving a specific educational result of the pedagogue and the learner (child): acquisition of knowledge, formation of skills and abilities, development of abilities, formation of moral qualities and habits. is a method of operation. Different methods are used in the process of introducing children to nature in kindergarten.

Methods of introduction to nature are divided into three main groups: visual method - observation, viewing pictures, slides, motion pictures, excursions; practical method - game method, work, simple experiments; oral method - teacher's story, reading works of art, conversation. When choosing methods, the educator adapts to the age characteristics of children, psychology, knowledge, program requirements, the nature of the climate of their country, and pedagogical principles. The above methods are interrelated and complement each other.

Demonstration method of introduction to nature. Observation method. In introducing children to nature in different age groups, the educator widely uses the visual method - observation. Observation is the perception of natural objects and events in natural conditions with the senses without directly interfering with the course of these events. Observation is a complex cognitive activity that involves perception, thinking, and speech, and requires sustained attention. Constant observations in introducing children to nature are of great importance in developing their logical thinking and speech. K.D. Ushinsky says: "True human, intellectual speech consists in sound reasoning, and sound reasoning, as we have shown, comes from real and clear observations, not from anything else." If children are introduced to objects and events in nature in a certain order, their attention and observation, interest in nature, and the desire to know its events will increase.

Observation is a very important feature, in which the child develops the ability to write correctly and speak. It is necessary to teach children to learn events and things according to their purpose and to distinguish the most important of them. Educators should teach children to learn the connection between things and events and causal connections while conducting observation work. In this way, the thinking of children of preschool age grows by accumulating concrete knowledge about nature. Observations can only be carried out by attracting attention. By learning to observe, that is, to draw attention to things and events in a purposeful way, we also develop voluntary attention in them. Correcting misconceptions is much more difficult than creating new ones. Therefore, it is very important for children to

have the correct understanding of nature, based on sensory experiences, even at the age of preschool education.

It is necessary to cultivate interest in nature in children, because it can arise even in unhealthy activities. For example, children catch beetles and butterflies and cut off their wings and legs, wondering what they are doing. Or they torture animals and birds and wonder what the result will be. It is necessary to explain to them the interconnectedness of nature, that is, that it is a "golden chain". Through this, children are given ecological education. "A close relationship with nature teaches interest in knowing together with observation. This is based on the reflex of speculation and investigation, and its extreme development is a characteristic of a person," believes I.P. Pavlov. "What is this?", "Why?", "How?" endless questions such as

In this case, the teacher should try to involve the children in finding answers to the questions. When organizing observations in different age groups of children of preschool age, the educator uses its various types. Observations can be short-term or long-term in terms of duration and nature. A more complex type of observation - long-term observations - is used to accumulate knowledge about the growth and development of plants and animals, seasonal changes in nature. In this case, children have to compare the observed state of the object with the previous one. Observation is also organized in order to determine the condition of things based on certain signs (for example, to water a flower based on its leaf, to change the water based on the state of the water in the aquarium, or to determine which bird's footprint is based on the track in the snow, to distinguish whether the fruits are ripe or raw by color). This type of observation helps children to develop the skills of analyzing natural phenomena, comparing some information, and drawing simpler conclusions. Due to the complexity of the content of comparisons and long-term observations, it is used in preschool, secondary, senior and preparatory groups. During these observations, the process of analyzing, comparing, drawing conclusions improves in children. According to the content of the observations and the goal set by the educator, excursions, walks, and activities in the nature corner are organized with plants and animals, weather, and the work of adults in nature. In the process of short-term observation, children learn to distinguish the shape, color, size, structure, spatial location, surface character of objects, and when they get to know animals, they learn the nature of movement and the sounds they emit. This type of observation includes, for example, the occurrence of snow or rain, the formation of a rainbow. In all cases, observation should develop children's high mental activity, encourage them to think, find answers to the questions, as well as develop their interests and educate them to be careful with nature. Educator preparation for observation. The choice of object is of great importance in the organization of observation.

The chosen object must be in good condition, that is, the plant must not wither, the varieties must not be packed, the animal must be trained, healthy, and not afraid of children. If the observation is in the corner of nature, the object should be well lit, and the light should fall from the side so that it is convenient to approach it. Children can feed, pet, and play with animals while watching their movements. It is necessary for animals to behave freely and move freely. For this, it is advisable for children to sit comfortably in the corner of nature.

Manage tracking.

If the teacher is conducting the observation for the first time, he watches the children for at least 1-2 minutes in order to satisfy their interests and to form a first impression of what is being observed. In the process of controlling observation, the teacher uses various methods -

questions and tasks suitable for the children's age, holding things, comparing, playing activities. While organizing the observation, the teacher must tell the necessary information, distinguish the important features of the observed object. In order to arouse children's interest in observation and aesthetic perception of observed things, the educator uses poems, riddles, and in older age groups, reading works of art. When observing the animals, the educator observes consistency and draws the children's attention to "What is it doing?" "How's it going?" "What is he eating?" "How is he eating?" "What is his body covered with?" "What are his legs like - long or short?" "What are his eyes (shape, color)?" focuses on the behavior of animals using questions like Observing plants begins with marking and distinguishing their most prominent, visible signs. It can be the flower of a plant or its brightly colored leaves, sometimes a stem (for example, a cactus). After that, the main characteristics of the external structure of the plant - size, shape, stem (or trunk), leaves, flowers, etc. are considered in order. Such consistency is necessary due to the fact that the attention of children of preschool age is not stable enough, and in many ways they are involuntary.

However, at the end of the training, it is necessary to summarize the results of the ideas that appeared during the observation process. In all cases, when the educator organizes observation, he should observe consistency in moving from one specific task to another, from facts to connections, from collecting ideas to comparing them, and then drawing conclusions. Then children develop logical thinking. In each observation, it is necessary to solve a small, specific task of introducing children to nature. Therefore, it is necessary to connect each observation with the previous one. When organizing a long-term observation, the educator divides it in advance into a series of episodic observations - "pieces". Such observation is carried out when changes in the development of plants are clearly visible. The teacher advises the children to watch the plant and note its signs (seeing the appearance of the first leaves, the emergence of the seed coat). In the final observation, children should restore the entire picture of the observed plant development. This observation can be organized on the basis of a diary, various pictures, herbariums, and in large age groups, graphic tables. Observation using handouts. These observations are carried out starting from middle age groups.

Organization of such observation is much more complicated than observation of a single object. In this case, the educator is required to be able to divide his attention, to be able to organize the movement of the children, and the children must strictly follow all the instructions of the educator, listen to each other, and compare the observations of others with their own observations. This method of observation has great developmental value. Children will have the opportunity to improve their academic skills through various research activities. This, in turn, helps them to form more accurate ideas. Plants and their leaves, fruits, seeds, branches, as well as vegetables and fruits are widely used as distribution material.

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